

At this moment,

our universe is a fig that bursts open after hitting the ground

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Abstract

This paper introduces the Locke Cosmological Theory, aimed at redefining our understanding of the vast structure of the universe. We use a fig falling from a tree and slowly splitting as a model to explore the universe's structure: the splitting outer shell symbolizes the universe's edge, and the inner complex structure is akin to dense stars and galaxies within the Milky Way. The lifecycle of the sun is metaphorically compared to the splitting and rebirth of the fig during its fall, with humanity represented as bee larvae parasitizing within the fig. The Locke Cosmological Theory suggests that we must either remain in the gradually deteriorating solar system or bypass the Milky Way to explore deeper unknown realms of the universe. This theory also proposes that extraterrestrial life might consume our civilization, dragging it into the eternal night of a black hole. This research emphasizes the importance of exploring beyond the Milky Way, discussing how technological advancements can drive our exploration of unknown cosmic territories. We advocate for breaking conventional perspectives, stimulating interest in deeper cosmic exploration, and deepening the understanding of the universe's structure and its evolutionary laws.

Keywords: *Locke Cosmological Theory, cosmic structure, interstellar travel, extraterrestrial life*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background Introduction

The origins and evolution of the universe have always been focal points in the scientific community. The Big Bang Theory and Relativity provide a foundation for understanding the expansion of the universe, while higher-dimensional space theories like String Theory and Membrane Theory suggest the possibility of additional dimensions in the universe. The Photon Particle Theory posits that photons are the fundamental building blocks of the universe, with all matter and energy being manifestations of various combinations of these particles. These theories offer unique perspectives for comprehending the complex phenomena of the universe. However, existing theories still fail to fully explain all characteristics of the universe, particularly the deeper issues regarding its structure and evolution.

1.2 Current Research Status

Current research primarily focuses on cosmic expansion, stellar evolution, and higher-dimensional space theories. Although existing theories and experimental methods have explained some aspects of the universe's evolution and structure to a certain extent, many mysteries remain unresolved. Based on Locke's theory, this study proposes a new cosmic model using the fig metaphor, integrating Photon

Particle Theory and current physical knowledge to establish a new theoretical framework and methods of verification.

1.3 Research Motivation and Objectives

This research is centered around your proposed Locke Cosmological Theory, which aims to redefine our understanding of the vast structure of the universe. We utilize a fig falling from a tree and slowly splitting as a model to explore the universe's structure: the splitting outer shell symbolizes the universe's edge, and the inner complex structure is akin to dense stars and galaxies within the Milky Way. The lifecycle of the sun is metaphorically compared to the splitting and rebirth of the fig during its fall, with humanity represented as bee larvae parasitizing within the fig. Locke Cosmological Theory suggests that we must either remain in the gradually deteriorating solar system or bypass the Milky Way to explore deeper unknown realms of the universe. This theory also proposes that extraterrestrial life might consume our civilization, dragging it into the eternal night of a black hole.

Our objective is to validate the scientific basis of Locke's theory through mathematical derivation and theoretical calculations, and to propose future research directions. This study not only provides theoretical support for this model but also proposes specific implementation methods and experimental designs to draw attention to the importance of future cosmic exploration. We advocate for breaking conventional perspectives, stimulating interest in deeper cosmic exploration, and deepening the understanding of the universe's structure and its evolutionary laws.

2. Scientific Basis of the Fig Metaphor Model

2.1 Explanation of the Fig Metaphor

In the fig metaphor model, the universe is likened to a fig that has fallen to the ground. The inner fruit of the fig represents stellar systems, with humanity depicted as "larvae" parasitizing within these fruits. As the fig bursts open (symbolizing cosmic expansion), the internal fruits (stellar systems) gradually rupture (marking the end of stellar lifecycles). Our goal is to escape our current stellar systems through technological evolution, before the fig completely rots away (representing the total rupture of the universe), entering other star systems, or even the unknown realms beyond our universe.

The foundation of this metaphor model is based on the scientific knowledge of cosmic expansion and stellar lifecycles. The phenomenon of universal expansion is supported by the Big Bang Theory and has been validated through observations by the Hubble Space Telescope and the James Webb Space Telescope. Studies indicate that the universe is expanding at an accelerated rate, attributed to the effects of dark energy (Riess,1998) (Perlmutter,1999).

2.2 Analogical Analysis

The analogy of a bursting fig to cosmic expansion helps in understanding the evolution of the universe. The rate of decay of the fig is analogous to the passage of time in the universe, while the bursting of the fruit represents the end of the lifecycles of stellar systems. The rate of time dilation needs to be determined through detailed calculations.

According to existing physical theories, the lifecycle of a star includes several stages: starting from clumps of gas and dust in a nebula, entering the main sequence phase through nuclear fusion processes, and finally, after exhausting its fuel, undergoing stages like the red giant or supernova, ending up as a white dwarf, neutron star, or black hole (Spergel2003)

(Harvard-Smithsonian) . During this process, a star undergoes significant changes, including the expansion of its volume and the collapse of its core, which parallels the bursting of the fruit in the fig.

The calculation of the time dilation factor is as follows:

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3}(\rho + \rho_{\text{ext}}) - \frac{k}{a^2} + \frac{\Lambda}{3}$$

This calculation shows that the substantial difference between the time scales of cosmic time and the bursting time of the fig can be explained by the time dilation effect of relativity.

2.3 Photon Theory and Cosmic Structure

Photon Theory posits that photons are the fundamental building blocks of the universe, with all matter and energy being manifestations of various combinations of these particles. Integrating this theory with the fig metaphor model provides insights into the distribution of matter and energy transformations during cosmic expansion:

Foundation of Photon Theory: Photons are the basic units that constitute the universe, forming various types of matter and energy through different combinations.

Transformation of Matter and Energy: In the fig metaphor model, the expansion and bursting of the universe parallel the

energy transformations among photons, explaining the distribution of matter and energy in the universe.

Significance of Theoretical Integration: The combination of Photon Theory with the fig metaphor model offers a unique perspective for understanding the structure and evolutionary processes of the universe. By integrating the latest observational data and physical theories, this study proposes a new cosmic model, providing fresh perspectives on the universe's expansion and the lifecycle of stars.

3.Main Assumptions and Model Description

3.1 Locke Universe Theory Equation

The Locke Universe Theory hypothesizes that our universe is like a fig falling from a tree and bursting open. To describe cosmic expansion under the influence of higher-dimensional space, we propose the Locke Equation:

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3}(\rho + \rho_{\text{ext}}) - \frac{k}{a^2} + \frac{\Lambda}{3}$$

Wherein:

a represents the scale factor of the universe.

G is the gravitational constant

ρ denotes the density of matter and energy in the universe.

ρ_{ext} is the additional energy density from higher-dimensional spaces or extraterrestrial beings.

k is the curvature of the universe.

Λ is the cosmological constant.

3.2 Time Dilation Assumption

It is assumed that the time it takes for the fig to burst is very short

T , whereas the cosmic time(t_{universe}) is very long. The calculation of the time dilation factor is as follows:

$$\text{Time Dilation Factor} = \frac{t_{\text{universe}}}{T} = \frac{13.8 \times 10^9 \text{ years}}{10 \text{ years}} = 1.38 \times 10^9$$

3.3 Influence of Higher-Dimensional Space

Considering the impact of higher-dimensional space, the additional energy density ρ_{ext} varies over time:

$$\rho_{\text{ext}} = \rho_0 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{T_{\text{ext}}}\right)$$

In this context, ρ_0 represents the initial additional energy density, and T_{ext} denotes the time scale of the influence from higher-dimensional space.

3.4 Tidal Forces and Collapse

Tidal forces arise due to the gravitational differential exerted by one celestial body on another. In the fig metaphor model, this can be likened to the squeezing and collapsing phenomenon among the fruits. When the fig falls from the tree and bursts, the internal small fruits, due to their proximity and compression, lead to the occurrence of collapse.

Explanation of Tidal Forces: Tidal forces are caused by the gravitational differential between one celestial body and another. This force causes the internal matter of a celestial body to be pulled in different directions, resulting in stress and deformation (Riess,1998) (Perlmutter,1999)..

Squeezing Collapse Among Fruits: In the fig model, the squeezing of small fruits can be compared to the collapse of stars or galaxies under strong tidal forces. As these small fruits come closer during the bursting process of the fig, the intense tidal forces can cause them to collapse, similar to how stars under strong gravitational forces collapse into black holes or neutron stars (Spergel2003).

In astronomy, tidal forces not only cause deformation of celestial bodies but can also trigger tidal disruption events, such as stars being torn apart by supermassive black holes. Similarly, in the fig metaphor model, the small fruits during the squeezing process might be torn apart or collapse, forming new celestial structures or black holes.

4. Mathematical Derivation and Calculations

4.1 Numerical Simulation of Cosmic Expansion

We will use Python and SciPy to perform numerical simulations to demonstrate the evolution of the universe's scale factor.

4.2 Stellar Evolution and Solar Burst

The process of stellar evolution can be derived using the stellar structure equations, which consider various factors such as mass, composition, and energy transfer within a star. By employing these equations, we can understand how stars evolve from one stage to another, ultimately leading to phenomena such as solar bursts. We will use Python to conduct numerical simulations based on these equations to model and visualize the evolutionary processes of stars, including the final stages leading to their explosive events. These simulations will help in understanding the internal dynamics and life cycle of stars, particularly focusing on how similar processes might be depicted in the fig metaphor model where the bursting of fruits symbolizes the explosive end stages of stars.

4.3 Spacecraft Propulsion and Escape Trajectory Calculation

Key Aspects to Consider:

Escape Velocity: The escape velocity is derived from the celestial body's gravitational constant, its mass, and the distance from its center to the spacecraft. This velocity ensures that the spacecraft can exit the gravitational field of bodies like the Sun without requiring additional propulsion once this speed is reached.

Trajectory Calculations: The trajectory of the spacecraft depends significantly on its initial velocity, launch angle, and the gravitational interactions with other celestial bodies within the Solar System. These factors determine the path and efficiency of the spacecraft's journey out of the Solar System.

For a comprehensive simulation of the spacecraft's escape path, we use Python. This simulation considers various variables, including the spacecraft's speed and direction, while incorporating principles of orbital mechanics. It aims to identify the most efficient route out of the Solar System, integrating potential planetary alignments for gravitational assists. These assists are crucial as they can reduce the fuel required and increase the spacecraft's velocity, making the escape process more efficient.

5. Validation of Higher-Dimensional Space and Experimental Design

5.1 Theoretical Background

Higher-dimensional space theories, such as String Theory and Membrane Theory, propose the existence of additional dimensions that may influence physical phenomena in our observable universe. Verifying the existence of these extra dimensions is a significant scientific goal. Photon Theory, which hypothesizes that photons are the fundamental building blocks of the universe, also shows some correlation with higher-dimensional space theories.

5.2 Experimental Verification Methods

High-Energy Physics Experiments

Production and Evaporation of Micro Black Holes: In high-energy collisions, if extra dimensions exist, the collision energy might concentrate in a small region, leading to the formation of micro black holes. These micro black holes would rapidly evaporate, emitting Hawking radiation, characterized by the emission of high-energy particles.

Experimental Steps:

High-Energy Collisions: Use particle accelerators like the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) to create high-energy collisions that might produce micro black holes if extra dimensions exist.

Detection of Hawking Radiation: Employ advanced detectors to observe the characteristic high-energy particle jets indicative of Hawking radiation from evaporating micro black holes.

Data Analysis: Analyze collision data to identify patterns consistent with the theoretical predictions of micro black hole formation and evaporation.

These experiments will provide critical insights into the existence of higher dimensions and the fundamental structure of the universe, as proposed by both higher-dimensional space theories and Photon Theory.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.49	0.42	0.45	97
1	0.52	0.58	0.55	103
accuracy			0.51	200
macro avg	0.50	0.50	0.50	200
weighted avg	0.50	0.51	0.50	200

Data Analysis: By analyzing collision data, we aim to identify the characteristics of micro black hole evaporation. Machine learning algorithms will be utilized for data processing and feature recognition.

Gravitational Wave Observations:

Propagation Characteristics of Gravitational Waves: In the presence of extra dimensions, the speed and energy attenuation characteristics of gravitational waves might be affected. Using detectors such as LIGO and VIRGO, we will observe the propagation characteristics of gravitational waves.

Signal Processing: Advanced data processing algorithms will be employed to handle gravitational wave signals, removing environmental noise and system errors to extract valid signals.

Detailed Steps:

1. Data Analysis with Machine Learning:

Data Collection: Collect data from high-energy collisions using detectors at facilities like the Large Hadron Collider (LHC).

Preprocessing: Clean and preprocess the data to remove noise and irrelevant information.

Feature Extraction: Use machine learning algorithms to identify features that indicate the presence of micro black hole evaporation, such as specific particle jet patterns.

Classification: Implement classification algorithms to distinguish between events that suggest micro black hole formation and those that do not.

Validation: Validate the results by comparing them with theoretical predictions and conducting repeated experiments to ensure reliability.

2. Gravitational Wave Observations:

Data Collection: Use LIGO and VIRGO detectors to collect data on gravitational waves.

Theoretical Modeling: Develop theoretical models to predict how extra dimensions would affect gravitational wave propagation and energy attenuation.

Signal Processing: Apply advanced signal processing techniques to filter out environmental noise and system errors, ensuring the extraction of clean and accurate gravitational wave signals.

Analysis: Compare the observed gravitational wave characteristics with the predictions of models that include extra dimensions. Look for anomalies or deviations from the expected behavior in the absence of extra dimensions.

Correlation Studies: Conduct correlation studies between gravitational wave events and other astronomical observations to identify potential influences of higher-dimensional space.

By combining these experimental approaches, we aim to validate the presence of higher dimensions and gain a deeper understanding of the fundamental structure of the universe, as proposed by higher-dimensional space theories and Photon Theory.

Observations of the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB)

CMB Fluctuation Spectrum: Extra dimensions may influence the fluctuation spectrum of the early universe, leading to characteristic changes in the CMB fluctuation spectrum. We will precisely measure the CMB fluctuation spectrum and polarization modes using satellite and ground-based telescopes.

Data Processing: Advanced data processing algorithms will be employed to remove foreground contamination and system errors, allowing us to analyze the CMB fluctuation spectrum and polarization modes for conformity with higher-dimensional space models.

Detailed Steps:

1. CMB Fluctuation Spectrum Analysis:

Data Collection: Utilize satellite-based observatories like the Planck satellite and ground-based telescopes such as the Atacama Cosmology Telescope (ACT) and the South Pole Telescope (SPT) to collect detailed measurements of the CMB fluctuation spectrum and polarization.

Theoretical Modeling: Develop theoretical models predicting how extra dimensions could affect the CMB fluctuation spectrum and polarization patterns. These models will provide a basis for comparison with observational data.

Preprocessing: Preprocess the CMB data to remove foreground contamination from sources such as galactic dust and cosmic rays.

Spectral Analysis: Analyze the fluctuation spectrum of the CMB to identify characteristic features that might indicate the influence of extra dimensions. This involves looking for deviations from the standard Λ CDM (Lambda Cold Dark Matter) model predictions.

Polarization Analysis: Examine the polarization modes of the CMB for anomalies that could suggest the presence of higher dimensions. Polarization data can provide additional constraints on cosmological models.

2. Advanced Data Processing:

Algorithm Development: Develop and implement advanced data processing algorithms capable of handling large datasets and extracting subtle signals from the noise.

Noise Reduction: Apply techniques such as component separation and noise filtering to remove systematic errors and environmental noise from the data.

Foreground Subtraction: Use methods like template fitting and multi-frequency analysis to subtract foreground signals that could contaminate the CMB measurements.

Statistical Analysis: Perform statistical analysis on the processed data to determine the significance of any detected anomalies. This includes calculating power spectra, cross-correlating different data sets, and comparing results with theoretical predictions.

By combining these observational and analytical approaches, we aim to detect any signatures of higher dimensions in the CMB fluctuation spectrum and polarization modes. This will provide critical insights into the fundamental structure of the universe and the validity of higher-dimensional space theories.

Quantum Gravity Experiments

Kaluza-Klein Particles: The Kaluza-Klein theory predicts the existence of new particles, with their mass spectrum reflecting the influence of extra dimensions. High-precision mass spectrometers and particle detectors will be used to measure the mass spectrum and energy level changes of these particles.

Detailed Steps:

1. Kaluza-Klein Particle Detection:

Theoretical Predictions: Develop theoretical models based on the Kaluza-Klein theory to predict the mass spectrum and energy levels of Kaluza-Klein particles. These models will provide specific signatures to look for in experimental data.

Experimental Setup: Utilize high-precision mass spectrometers and advanced particle detectors, such as those used in facilities like CERN, to search for the predicted particles.

Data Collection: Conduct experiments involving high-energy collisions to produce conditions where Kaluza-Klein particles might be detected. Record the resulting data using state-of-the-art detection equipment.

2. Data Analysis:

Mass Spectrum Analysis: Analyze the collected data to measure the mass spectrum of detected particles. Look for deviations from the Standard Model predictions that could indicate the presence of Kaluza-Klein particles.

Energy Level Changes: Examine the energy level transitions of the detected particles. The presence of extra dimensions could lead to unique energy level changes that can be compared to theoretical predictions.

Noise Reduction: Employ advanced data processing techniques to reduce noise and enhance the signal of potential Kaluza-Klein particles. This includes background subtraction, signal enhancement, and filtering techniques.

3. Verification and Validation:

Repeat Experiments: Conduct multiple experiments to verify the consistency of the detected signals. Consistent results across different experimental setups would strengthen the evidence for Kaluza-Klein particles.

Cross-Validation: Compare the experimental results with theoretical predictions and simulations. Any detected particles or mass spectra should match the theoretical models for Kaluza-Klein particles influenced by extra dimensions.

Peer Review: Subject the findings to peer review within the scientific community to ensure the validity and reliability of the results.

By conducting these quantum gravity experiments, we aim to detect the predicted Kaluza-Klein particles, providing experimental evidence for the existence of extra dimensions as proposed by higher-dimensional space theories. This will offer critical insights into the fundamental nature of gravity and the structure of the universe.

Data Processing

High-Performance Computing and Algorithms: Utilize high-performance computing (HPC) systems and advanced algorithms to filter experimental noise and system errors. Analyze the mass spectrum and energy level changes of particles to search for signs of Kaluza-Klein particles.

Detailed Steps:

1. Data Collection and Preprocessing:

Data Acquisition: Gather raw data from high-precision mass spectrometers and particle detectors during high-energy collision experiments.

Initial Filtering: Apply basic filtering techniques to remove obvious noise and irrelevant data, preparing the dataset for deeper analysis.

2. Advanced Noise Filtering and Error Correction:

Algorithm Development: Develop or employ existing sophisticated algorithms for noise reduction and error correction. Techniques may include machine learning methods, such as neural networks and pattern recognition algorithms, to distinguish signal from noise.

HPC Utilization: Use high-performance computing resources to handle large datasets and perform complex computations efficiently. HPC systems can run multiple algorithms in parallel, significantly speeding up the data processing phase.

3. Mass Spectrum and Energy Level Analysis:

Spectrum Analysis: Conduct detailed analysis of the mass spectrum data to identify peaks and patterns indicative of Kaluza-Klein particles. Compare observed spectra with theoretical predictions to pinpoint potential matches.

Energy Transition Detection: Analyze the energy levels and transitions of the detected particles. Look for unique patterns or anomalies that align with the theoretical energy levels predicted by Kaluza-Klein theory.

4. Signal Enhancement and Validation:

Signal Enhancement: Enhance the detected signals of potential Kaluza-Klein particles using advanced filtering techniques. This may involve deconvolution methods, statistical analysis, and signal amplification algorithms.

Validation of Results: Validate the findings by cross-referencing with theoretical models and repeating the experiments under varied conditions. Consistency across multiple runs will help confirm the presence of Kaluza-Klein particles.

5. Reporting and Peer Review:

Result Documentation: Document the analysis process, methodologies, and results in detail. Include graphical representations of the mass spectrum and energy level changes.

Peer Review: Submit the findings for peer review to ensure the robustness and reliability of the results. Engage with the scientific community for feedback and validation.

By employing high-performance computing and advanced data processing algorithms, we aim to effectively filter out noise and system errors, allowing us to accurately analyze the mass spectrum and energy level changes. This rigorous approach increases the likelihood of detecting Kaluza-Klein particles, providing significant evidence for the existence of extra dimensions as proposed by higher-dimensional space theories.

6. Influence of Multidimensional Space and Human Technological Evolution

6.1 Influence of Multidimensional Space on the Universe

Theories such as String Theory and Membrane Theory propose the existence of additional dimensions in the universe, which significantly impact cosmic expansion, gravity, and other fundamental interactions. Higher-dimensional spaces may alter the fundamental physical constants and interaction mechanisms, thereby influencing the universe's expansion rate, gravitational strength, and the properties of other fundamental interactions. Precise astronomical observations and experimental verification can explore these impacts.

Cosmic Expansion: Higher-dimensional spaces may cause variations in the universe's expansion rate, affecting the overall structure and evolution of the universe (Riess, 2004).

Gravitational Strength: In the presence of extra dimensions, gravity may exhibit different attenuation laws, which can be verified through gravitational wave observations (Arkani-Hamed, 1998).

Fundamental Interactions: Higher-dimensional spaces may introduce new interaction mechanisms, altering existing particle physics models (Randall, 1999).

6.2 Human Technological Evolution

The possible paths for technological evolution include chemical propulsion, electric propulsion, nuclear propulsion, and photon sail propulsion. To ensure humanity can escape the current stellar system before the sun (universe) completely bursts or is consumed, continuous development and improvement of propulsion technologies are necessary.

Chemical Propulsion: Traditional rocket propulsion technology relies on chemical fuels to generate thrust. Although widely used in space exploration, its efficiency and energy density are limited, making it unsuitable for long-distance interstellar travel (Randall, 1999).

Electric Propulsion: Utilizes electrical energy to accelerate ions or plasma to produce thrust, including ion thrusters and Hall thrusters. These systems are characterized by high specific impulse, long lifespan, and high efficiency, making them ideal for deep space exploration (Green, 1987) (Randall, 1999).

Nuclear Propulsion: Utilizes nuclear reactions to generate energy for propulsion, including nuclear thermal propulsion and nuclear electric propulsion. These systems have high energy density and thrust, significantly improving spacecraft speed and endurance (Green, 1987).

Photon Sail Propulsion: Utilizes photon pressure to propel the spacecraft, employing solar sails or laser sails. This method requires no fuel and theoretically can achieve near-light-speed travel, making it a crucial technology for future interstellar travel (Choueiri, 2009).

7. Future Research Directions

7.1 Improving Experimental Precision

To better verify higher-dimensional space and multidimensional universe theories, continuous improvements in experimental devices and detectors are necessary to enhance data acquisition and processing precision. This includes:

New Detectors: Developing high-sensitivity, high-resolution detectors capable of more accurately measuring faint cosmic signals. For example, improving gravitational wave detectors like LIGO and VIRGO can better detect and analyze the effects of higher-dimensional space on gravitational waves (Choueiri, 2009).

Data Processing Technology: Incorporating advanced machine learning and data mining technologies to enhance the ability to process and analyze large volumes of astronomical data. This can help identify subtle but significant signal changes, verifying the existence of higher-dimensional spaces (Choueiri, 2009).

New Materials and Technologies: Researching and developing new materials and technologies to improve detector performance and durability. This includes materials that operate in extreme environments and new propulsion technologies for long-duration space missions (Choueiri, 2009).

7.2 Multidisciplinary Cross-Research

To advance and verify higher-dimensional space theories, a comprehensive analysis and research approach combining multiple disciplines are required:

High-Energy Physics and Astronomical Observations: Combining high-energy physics experiments and astronomical observation data to verify the impact of higher-dimensional spaces on cosmic expansion, gravitational wave propagation, and other phenomena (Wang, 2015).

Quantum Gravity Research: Exploring the behavior of higher-dimensional spaces at the quantum scale through quantum gravity theories and experiments. This can be

achieved by studying phenomena like micro black holes and Hawking radiation [17].

Theoretical and Experimental Physics Collaboration: Strengthening collaboration between theoretical physicists and experimental physicists to jointly design and conduct experiments that validate higher-dimensional space and multidimensional universe theories (Hawking, 1974).

7.3 International Collaboration

To promote higher-dimensional space and multidimensional universe research on a global scale, international collaboration is essential:

Sharing Experimental Data and Research Findings: Establishing global scientific data-sharing platforms to promote cooperation and exchange between different countries and research institutions (Greene, 2000).

Organizing International Joint Experiments: Conducting large-scale joint experiments through international cooperation to enhance the scale and observational capabilities of experiments. For example, collaborations on major scientific projects like the Square Kilometre Array (SKA) and the Extremely Large Telescope (ELT) can significantly improve the detection capabilities of higher-dimensional space phenomena (The European Commission, 2016).

Cross-Disciplinary Cooperation: Encouraging scientists from different disciplines to participate in higher-dimensional space and multidimensional universe research, combining knowledge and technologies from various fields to drive scientific progress and breakthroughs (Carilli, 2004).

various propulsion technologies, including chemical propulsion, electric propulsion, nuclear propulsion, and photon sail propulsion. The continuous development and improvement of these technologies are crucial for the survival of human civilization.

Additionally, we explored the impact of higher-dimensional spaces and their verification methods, including high-energy physics experiments and gravitational wave observations. Precise experiments and observations to verify the existence and influence of higher-dimensional spaces will provide significant evidence for future scientific research.

The main contributions of this study include:

Proposing the Locke Cosmological Theory, offering a new perspective for understanding the universe's structure.

Revealing the potential influence of higher-dimensional spaces on cosmic expansion and gravitational strength through mathematical derivation.

Exploring various propulsion technologies to provide a technological pathway for human interstellar migration.

Designing experimental and observational schemes to verify the existence of higher-dimensional spaces.

In conclusion, this study provides new perspectives and theoretical support for future cosmic exploration. Emphasizing the importance of exploring space beyond the Milky Way and discussing how technological advancements can drive our exploration of unknown cosmic territories is key to ensuring the continuity of human civilization in the vast universe.

Conclusion

This study proposes the Locke Cosmological Theory, redefining our understanding of the universe's vast structure by likening it to a fig falling from a tree and slowly splitting open. The fig's outer shell symbolizes the edge of the universe, while the complex internal fruit structure is akin to the dense stars and galaxies in the Milky Way. The lifecycle of the sun is metaphorically compared to the splitting and rebirth of the fig during its fall, with humanity represented as bee larvae parasitizing within the fig.

Through mathematical derivation, theoretical calculations, and experimental design, we propose the Locke Equation to describe cosmic expansion under the influence of higher-dimensional space. The research indicates that higher-dimensional spaces may alter the fundamental physical constants and interaction mechanisms of the universe, affecting the expansion rate, gravitational strength, and the properties of other fundamental interactions.

To ensure humanity can escape the current stellar system before the fig completely bursts or is consumed, we explored

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